

Representation of Feminist Women/ Feminism in Indian Visual Media

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Abstract

India has seen a rise in the number of female-centred shows and movies. We can watch many shows, labelled and marketed as feminist, being produced nowadays. However, not all the shows claiming to be feminist are actually so. Sometimes, a director and a writer who do not understand feminism themselves end up creating a show or a movie that is filled with pseudo-feminism and man-hating in the name of feminism. This paper has selected two movies and a web series to analyze how feminism is depicted through Indian visual media. This paper discusses how mass media can impact and influence a society and how people believe everything that gets served to them through visual media. This paper argues that it is the responsibility of the makers to do their homework well; otherwise, their lack of knowledge and insensitivity may result in miseducating the masses.

Keywords: Feminism, visual media, representation, pseudo-feminism.

Introduction

Indian visual media has long portrayed women in secondary, ornamental, and sensuous roles. Laura Mulvey's *Visual Pleasure and Narrative Cinema* (1975) can be aptly used to analyze how the "male gaze" objectifies women on screen in Indian visual media. Mulvey argues that "in a world ordered by sexual imbalance, pleasure in looking has been split between active/male and passive/female" (p. 11). The camera angle, women's clothing, and the film's posters showing women in sensuous poses describe how the "male gaze" puts women in a position where they are the objects to be looked at for seeking pleasure, usually by the male subjects. She notes that women are "simultaneously looked at and displayed, with their appearance coded for strong visual and erotic impact" (Mulvey, 1975, p. 12). The starkest example of this can still be seen in Hindi item songs, where an actress is wearing short, exposing, sensuous clothes, and her visuals are being enjoyed by a male audience.

However, Indian visual media is also experiencing a rise in female-centred stories that portray women as independent, vocal, powerful, central characters. Movies like *Thappad* and *Pink* give social messages like "domestic violence is not okay and should not be normalized" and "no means no," respectively, which support women's position in society unlike the commercial movies that objectify women. While mainstream media still focuses mostly on heterosexual, high-class, English-speaking, rich, beautiful, young women, OTT platforms are

usually more experimental with their stories covering the marginalized and underrepresented women—Dalit, working-class, old, LGBTQIA+, poor, and rural women. Even in doing so, these shows are not free of the shadow of the “male gaze” and many times end up objectifying their female characters through exposing costumes, camera angles, and by using the “hotness” of these casts as a tool for promotion of the show.

Representation of any section of the society through media does not only depict the current status of that section in the society but also contributes to creating that status too. The power of mass media should be understood and handled sincerely by film and show creators, as these shows, once made public, help in creating and spreading new knowledge. In *Representation: Cultural Representations and Signifying Practices* (1997), Hall states that “representation is the production of meaning through language. It is an essential part of the process by which meaning is produced and exchanged” (p. 15). He suggests that media does not only reflect reality but also creates it: “Media representations do not merely reflect reality; they construct it” (Hall, 1997, p. 25). Filmmakers and show creators should keep in mind that their work should not only reflect reality but also aim towards creating a new, better, and more inclusive one. Films like *Thappad*, *Ek Ladki Ko Dekha To Aisa Laga*, and *Pink* should be applauded for attempting to spread a social message that help sensitize ordinary people towards sensitive topics like domestic violence, homosexuality, and consensual sex, respectively.

Social media, movies, TV shows, newspapers, and multiple different kinds of media platforms and mediums have served a huge role in spreading and supporting feminism as a movement. Representation through media helps educate the masses about things that may not be taught at universities and schools. Media can easily pass as the biggest tool for any movement to grow nowadays. But it can have its negative impact on the masses too. People believe whatever they see on social media or television as true without fact-checking or second-guessing it. They would believe even the misrepresentations of concepts shown on television. Misrepresentation of a feminist or the feminist movement on television can mis-educate people. Katz et al. (1973) state that “the significance of mass communication lies not in what it does to people, but in what people do with it” (p. 510), which suggests that people with violent tendencies would feel validated with movies like *Animal* and *Kabir Singh*, and women experiencing domestic violence would feel relieved after watching a movie like *Thappad*. Radway suggests that audiences would interpret Bollywood movies or OTT content depictions in a “dominant” way (accepting patriarchy) or a “negotiated/oppositional” way (resisting stereotypes) (Radway 1984).

Some of the contents that we see today on television depict feminism as everything that it is not. Lack of background check, knowledge, and sincerity on the part of the makers of a show or a movie can tarnish the image of the whole movement, and this can be seen happening in India. Indians have mixed feelings about feminism and feminists. While on one hand, good movies and shows are being made that help in educating the audience about feminism and its need in our society, on the other hand, social media is filled with either pseudo-feminists or people downright criticizing feminists and feminism. Students of literature, sociology, or any subject that requires the students to actually read important feminist writers may have

concrete knowledge of what the movement is actually about, but the majority of the masses, when they see misrepresented feminism on television, start making ill-informed beliefs about the movement and may become against it. It is because of such misrepresentation that many celebrities have shied away from associating themselves with the movement or calling themselves feminists in the past. The quote from The Hindu that “Actress Parineeti Chopra, the brand ambassador for Haryana’s *Beti Bachao Beti Padhao*’ campaign, says she is not a ‘feminist’ but strongly voices for gender equality” (PTI) shows how the definition of feminism is so misunderstood. Makers should understand their responsibility while choosing such sensitive topics and try to write a script with appropriate sincerity and seriousness. To analyze how feminism is depicted in Indian cinema and web series, three pieces of work—*Mrs.*, *Laapataa Ladies*, and *Four More Shots Please!*—are selected for this research paper.

Main body

Mrs., an Arati Kadav-directed movie written by Harman Baweja and Anu Singh Choudhary, is the story of a married Delhi girl, Richa, who is struggling to find her identity as a dance teacher after her arranged marriage with a gynecologist, Divakar. The movie establishes in the very beginning that Divakar is an orthodox man who is a strong believer in gender roles. On being told by Richa that the wedding gifts include two hot cases and a food processor, he responds by saying that “Sare gifts tumhare liye hi hain shayad/perhaps all the gifts are for you only” (Kadav, 2025). In another incident when Richa, in a drunk state, tells her friend that Divakar never helps her with the household chores, he replies, “Clinic mein bhi mai akele hi kaam karta hu, tum aati ho meri help karne?/ I work in the clinic alone too, do you come to help?” (Kadav, 2025), implying that Richa is as responsible for the household chores as he is for his job. By scenes like these, the director cleverly depicts how patriarchal men blur the line between obligation and choice for their convenience. In *Mr.*, Richa is not a submissive character and passively objects to the patriarchal male privileges her husband enjoys. In the very beginning of the story, we see that Divakar expects his wife to do everything that his mother has been doing for his father. He expects Richa to cook, clean, do his laundry, and even lay out his clothes on the bed for him as he takes a shower. Richa passively objects to this last demand when Divakar tells Richa to give him all his clothes for the day, which are in the cupboard, by saying, “Pehna bhi du?/Should I get you dressed too?” (Kadav, 2025) with a witty look on her face but continues to fulfil his demands. The different lives of Richa and her husband are exposed in this movie by showing Richa getting to bed late and waking up early to do the unending household chores while Divakar gets enough time to exercise, sleep well, and even play squash. Richa is shown trying to fit into the role of the ideal daughter-in-law and wife, but her work going unnoticed and unappreciated takes a toll on her patience. Richa’s husband expects Richa to offer herself in the bed to him every night even if she is tired after all the household chores but refuses to take Richa’s urges regarding her desires in bed into consideration and discards them by telling her, “Desire karne layak kuchh hai bhi tum mein? Kitchen ki baas aati hai tum mein se/ Is there anything desirable in you? You stink like the kitchen” (Kadav, 2025). Divakar’s hypocrisy is exposed here. He had told Richa in the initial days of their marriage regarding Richa smelling like the kitchen that “you smell like the kitchen, and it is the sexiest smell in the world” (Kadav,

2025), but now that Richa rejects his sexual advances and demands him to take her desires into consideration, the same kitchen-like smell becomes undesirable for him. In the climax scene of the movie, we see an outburst from Richa, which comes after many occasions of being unappreciated, ignored, looked down upon, yelled at, and denied the right to choose her own future course. Richa is denied the opportunity to work as a dance teacher and is asked to delete her online dance videos because, in the words of her father-in-law, “Humari family mein suit bhi nahi Karega/it will not even suit our family” (Kadav, 2025). It acts as the last blow Richa could take against her identity, which was already fading away in that family. After this, Richa finally rebels by breaking off her marriage and resuming her dance career.

This movie depicts so many problems that women face in their daily lives quite aptly by using so many useful metaphors, like Richa’s fading image in the boiling water in a pan to signify her fading identity into the household chores and the dripping water of the kitchen sink being filled in a bucket as Richa’s anger and discontent being piled up drop by drop. Finally, before walking out of the house, Richa throws that water on her husband during a fight. Some of that water falls on the father-in-law too, which represents that Richa’s patience with her husband and father-in-law is over. The kitchen pipeline is another metaphor for patriarchy, and Richa’s dialogue that “Ye leakage ki problem purani hai; poori pipeline hi badalni padegi/This leakage problem is old; the whole pipeline needs to be changed” (Kadav, 2025) means that the whole patriarchal system is quite old and needs to change completely. Despite the wonderful writing in the rest of the movie, the climax scene seems to be a little rushed over. On being yelled at by her husband and asked to make summer drinks for the guests while she was already struggling to hold on to her individuality after being asked by Divakar to delete her dance videos from social media, Richa reacts by serving the water being stored in a bucket under the kitchen sink to the guest who had come to the house for her father-in-law’s birthday. This enrages Divakar, and when he attempts to physically assault Richa, she throws the remaining water on him and walks out of that house. While this action is getting a lot of negative reactions from some viewers, it is important to understand that repressed anger does not always find the most rational mode of expression. On the other hand, her action can also not be justified as a reaction of an overworked Indian woman. In a similar situation, it is always best to not repress issues that are persistent and cannot be solved if left alone. There could have been other ways for Richa to express her anger, but this movie is not about how a woman should manage her anger in a toxic household but rather about how a simple, free-hearted, enthusiastic Richa, whose dreams and individuality are being crushed in her husband’s house, deals with her problems and comes out of it. In the final scene of the movie, Richa is shown to have resumed her career as a dance teacher and dancer, and her ex-husband is shown to have married again, and his new wife is now trying to fill the same position as Richa once did. While Richa’s reaction seems to have failed to raise any discussion or make any change in the dynamics of the family of her ex-husband, the movie’s message seems to be that not every action against patriarchy has to be a political statement or a movement; a woman simply saving herself from the clutches of a patriarchal, orthodox, and toxic family is remarkable enough to be celebrated.

Laapataa Ladies is a Kiran Rao-directed movie with a rural setting and a storyline about the misadventure of two newlywed brides who get lost from a train. It explores the stories of these two young women with two very different mindsets and hopes for life. While the young, innocent, and ignorant Phool wants to take care of her husband's house and is proud to be trained in all kinds of household chores, Jaya wants to study further and do great things in the field of agriculture. She is proud to have topped her exams and does not want to settle down. The movie depicts the problems and the mentality that come into a woman's life and a society with a simple veil. Phool, the simple woman who has no complaint against the veil and has no problem following her husband and following his instructions, is shown to be dependent on her husband and hopeless without him. She is so ignorant that she does not even remember the name of her husband's village, as she would not need to know anything as long as she is with her husband. Her world turns upside down when, in a confusion because of two veiled newlywed brides on the same seat, Deepak (Phool's husband) deboards the train with someone else's bride. This introduces us to our other central character, Jaya, who is an ambitious, clever, unorthodox, and independent woman. While Phool cannot even walk without staggering with a veil, Jaya manages to read the name of the village she is about to enter with Deepak. While Phool refuses to utter her husband's name and shows it on her henna tattoo, Jaya utters her husband's name loud and clear. The journey of these women is also completely different. While Phool waits for her husband to find her, Jaya tries to manage her college admissions by giving a fake name, a fake address, and fake whereabouts and even deceiving the police to get some time to plan her escape. While waiting for her husband to find her, Phool starts to work with Manju-tai on her tea stall at the railway station. With Manju-tai, Phool learns the importance of being financially independent, while Jaya helps Deepak find his wife. The movie ends with a little more empowered Phool and a Jaya who is free from her toxic marriage to study as much as she wants. Many feminist issues are discussed in the movie with great sensitivity and ease, which makes them seem natural and authentic. There is a scene in the movie where female sisterhood is discussed, and Yashoda (Deepak's mother) and her mother-in-law, who bickered at all times earlier, decide to give friendship among them a chance. Yashoda says, "Amma, aap-hum saheli ban sakte hain ka?/Amma, can you and I become friends?" (Rao, 2024), to which the mother-in-law replies, "Try Karen?!/Should we try?!" (Rao, 2024). In the same scene, Yashoda informs Jaya that she never cooks kamalkakri curry anymore even though she likes it a lot because her husband and son do not like it. On being asked by Jaya why she does not cook the curry for herself, she exclaims, "To ka ab auraton ke pasand ka khana Banega? / Will food that women like be cooked now?" (Rao, 2024), and laughs at Jaya's silly suggestion. In the end, when Jaya is leaving for her college, this same woman proudly gives Jaya a lunchbox and tells her, "Ye lo Kamalkakri ka sabji aur roti! Take this Kamalkakri curry and roti!" (Rao, 2024). It is remarkable how this movie covers so many issues that women still have in most parts of rural India, like dowry, repression, limiting them to the kitchen, internalized patriarchy, etc., and depicts them with such authenticity. This movie is a fine example of a tight script and detailed direction and writing and how a movie can be entertaining and impactful at the same time.

Four More Shots Please!, an Indian web series on Amazon Prime Video, is directed by Anu Menon and Nupur Asthana. The web series follows the story of four rich and educated

women from South Bombay, Anjana, Damini, Umang, and Siddhi, who are depicted as unapologetically flawed. Their story involves their love life, family, work life and the problems related to them, and how they deal with them. They are shown to fight their battles in their own “flawed” manners only to find solace in one another’s company. While posing as a feminist show, this show blurs the very thick line between feminism and man-hating, between woke feminists and obnoxiously delusional women who blame men and patriarchy for most of their problems, and between being unapologetic and being irresponsible. In a scene where these women meet four guys at a bar for the first time, they introduce themselves as

“Umang. I’m a trainer, bisexual, looking for adventure. Keep one word in mind: consent. No anal allowed. And oral? Only if you do it back.

I’m Anjana. A lawyer, a single mother. Oh and... my vagina refuses to come.

I’m Damini, startup founder... Super smart, Super successful. (She earns more than all four of your salaries combined). I also masturbate pretty often, much more efficient than sex.

I’m Siddhi, I’m a virgin. My mom hates me, she wants to get me married to a pure veg Gujju boy, but I love non veg. Unfortunately I can’t kick your ass today because I’m wearing very high heels. But what are your plans for tomorrow?” (Khanna)

Apparently, this is the picture of powerful women that the makers of the show attempt to paint through this scene. Cixous states that “Woman must write herself: must write about women and bring women to writing” (Cixous, 1975, p. 875). This show, which is directed, written, and shot by women, can serve as an example of how only men are not entitled to the male gaze; female show runners can also exhibit it. The camera angles, dialogues, costumes, and direction all scream male gaze instead of women's empowerment and feminism. The characters are objectified and made pleasing to the eyes at all times and speak the same gendered language that men do. For being sexist and hating men in general, they find an excuse in two thousand years of patriarchy. In a scene, Anjana cracks a sexist joke comparing men with condoms and on being told that it was a sexist joke, she says, “2000 years of patriarchy man! Ek joke to banta hai!! 2000 years of patriarchy, man! It deserves at least one joke!” (Menon and Asthana, 2019). Cheating is justified by making the characters “flawed,” but in the next moment they can be seen celebrating their messed-up decisions by toasting, “Here is to fuck-ups!” (Menon and Asthana, 2019). Using verbally offensive slang for no reason, like raising a toast to “kick it in the balls” (Menon and Asthana, 2019), is shown to be fun in the series. Although the series does touch upon many feminist issues like fat-shaming, gender discrimination in the workspace, miscarriage, the life of a woman after divorce, homophobia, etc., none of them are depicted with appropriate seriousness. The first season of this Amazon special series was "one of the top three most-watched Amazon Original Series from India in 2019" and was named "the most-watched Indian show on the platform" in May 2020 (Wikipedia contributors). The problem is that people who have not read the feminist theories watch such shows and either start following them or start hating a social movement like feminism without ever actually understanding it, neither of which is healthy for a society. Such shows serve to misinform and miseducate the masses. Shows dealing with such

sensitive topics should do so with appropriate seriousness and sincerity; otherwise, they will keep representing man-hating and vicarious lifestyle as feminism, and the true meaning of the movement will be lost in all the reactions and unnecessary discussion based on these shows.

Conclusion

This paper discusses how some movies in India, like *Mrs.* and *Laapataa Ladies*, depict women as powerful, independent, rational, and evolving beings, while other movies or shows, like *Four More Shots Please!*, depict them as pseudo-feminists who think that verbally abusing men, being toxic, consuming alcohol, having multiple affairs, and cheating on their partner is a show of power. This paper argues that visual media not only represent reality but also creates it. It is suggested in this paper that showrunners of India should feel responsible for the kind of content they circulate through their art and make sure that their depiction of any element of society does not get misrepresented. Many people learn through visual media, and when a concept is misrepresented on platforms like TV, movies, web series, YouTube videos, etc., masses get miseducated, and it impacts the well-being of our society. Being a feminist must be a choice, which can only be made after having thorough knowledge about this movement. In today's India, many people choose to be anti-feminist after watching misrepresentations of feminism and feminists in visual media. Media is a force that can sway the masses; thus, it should be handled with utmost care and responsibility. Showrunners choosing to deal with sensitive topics should only proceed after getting a thorough knowledge about them and create their piece of art with the appropriate seriousness and sincerity their chosen topic needs.

References

- Cixous, H. (1975). The laugh of the Medusa (K. Cohen & P. Cohen, Trans.). *Signs*, 1(4), 875–893. <https://doi.org/10.1086/493306>
- Hall, S. (1997). *Representation: Cultural representations and signifying practices*. Sage. (Original work published 1980)
- Kadav, A. (Director). (2025). *Mrs.* [Film]. Jio Studios; Baweja Studios.
- Katz, E., Blumler, J. G., & Gurevitch, M. (1973). Uses and gratifications research. *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 37(4), 509–523. <https://doi.org/10.1086/268109>
- Khanna, Mallika. “‘Four More Shots Please’ Gets Modern Indian Women Wrong - Kajal Magazine.” *Kajal Magazine*, 25 Mar. 2019, www.kajalmag.com/four-more-shots-please-gets-modern-indian-women-wrong.
- Mulvey, L. (1975). Visual pleasure and narrative cinema. *Screen*, 16(3), 6–18. <https://doi.org/10.1093/screen/16.3.6>
- Nandy, P., & Nandy, R. P. (Executive Producers). (2019). *Four more shots please!* [TV series]. Pritish Nandy Communications; Amazon Prime Video.

PTI. “I Am Not a Feminist’: Parineeti Chopra.” *The Hindu*, 14 Oct. 2015, www.thehindu.com/entertainment/i-am-not-a-feminist-parineeti-chopra/article7761881.ece.

Radway, J. A. (1984). *Reading the romance: Women, patriarchy, and popular literature*. University of North Carolina Press.

Rao, K. (Director). (2024). *Laapataa Ladies* [Film]. Aamir Khan Productions; Kindling Pictures; Jio Studios.

Wikipedia contributors. “Four More Shots Please!” *Wikipedia*, 14 Aug. 2025, en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Four_More_Shots_Please!